

Review

Calmodulin-protein 4.1R rendez-vous: Chaperon-like function for calmodulin and protein 4.1R in erythrocytes

Wataru Nunomura^{1,2*}, Hideki Wakui² and Yuichi Takakuwa³

¹Center for Geo-Environmental Science, Akita University, Akita 010-8502, Japan.

²Department of Life Science, Graduate School of Engineering and Resource Science, Akita University, Akita 010-8502, Japan

³Department of Biochemistry, Tokyo Women's Medical University, Kawada 8-1, Shinjuku, Tokyo 162-8666, Japan

* Corresponding author: Wataru Nunomura; Email: nunomura@gipc.akita-u.ac.jp

Abstract

An intriguing observation is that human erythrocytes can maintain their structural integrity over their 120-day life span despite the fact that they can no longer synthesize new proteins as they undergo enucleation upon maturation. Calmodulin (CaM), a canonical Ca²⁺ binding protein, plays a key role in keeping homeostasis of Ca²⁺ concentration in the cell through activation of Ca²⁺-ATPase. Membrane skeletal protein 4.1R is the prototypical member of a family of four highly paralogous proteins that include 4.1G, 4.1N and 4.1B. Human protein 4.1R is expressed as two major isoforms in the erythrocyte lineage, a 135kDa isoform (4.1R¹³⁵) expressed in erythroblasts but no longer expressed in mature erythrocytes and a 80kDa isoform (4.1R⁸⁰) expressed solely in mature erythrocytes. Interestingly, these two 4.1R isoforms, that differ by the presence or absence of an N-terminal 209 amino acid head-piece region (HP), have different CaM binding sites. Not only 4.1R¹³⁵ and 4.1R⁸⁰ differ by the location of their CaM binding sites but also by the way CaM regulates their interactions with other membrane proteins. Thus, whereas CaM binding to 4.1R¹³⁵ is strongly Ca²⁺-dependent and the dissociation constant in equilibrium (K_d) of their interaction is in the 10⁻⁸ M range, CaM binding to 4.1R⁸⁰ is Ca²⁺-independent and the K_d of this interaction is in the 10⁻⁷ M range both in the presence and absence of Ca²⁺. We have previously documented that the interaction of CaM with 4.1R⁸⁰ is physiologically important in maintaining the structural and mechanical properties of erythrocytes. Indeed, even in the absence of Ca²⁺, CaM promotes the thermostability of the 4.1R FERM (Four.one-Ezrin-Radixin-Moesin) domain through its interaction with a peptide encoded by exon 11, pep11 (A²⁶⁴KKLWKVCVEHHTFFRL). In this review, we discuss the structural functions of 4.1R⁸⁰ in erythrocytes, focusing primarily on the FERM domain, and propose a chaperon-like function for CaM and 4.1R⁸⁰ in erythrocytes based on our published data.

Keywords

protein 4.1R, calmodulin, membrane proteins

Abbreviations

4.1R⁸⁰, 80kDa human erythrocyte protein 4.1; 4.1R¹³⁵, 135kDa human erythroblast protein 4.1R; CaM, calmodulin; FERM, Four-one, Ezrin, Radixin, Moesin; GPC, glycoporphin C; HP, N-terminal head-piece region of 4.1 proteins; IOVs, inside-out-vesicles of human erythrocytes; K_d , dissociation constant at equilibrium; R30, 30kDa membrane binding FERM domain of protein 4.1R; RHP, headpiece region of protein 4.1R¹³⁵; RHP-R30, fusion protein of RHP and R30

Molecular structure of 4.1R

Structure of 4.1R

4.1R forms multi-molecular complexes with transmembrane proteins and membrane-associated proteins, such as spectrin and actin [1-9]. Such complexes, which are critical for maintaining structural stability in erythrocytes, are involved in other functions in non-erythroid cells such as, for example, signal transduction at sites of cell-cell and/or cell-matrix contacts.

4.1R⁸⁰ (accession ID:P11171), expressed at approximately 200,000 copies per erythrocyte, can be extracted by high salt treatment of inside-out vesicles (IOVs), which correspond to erythrocyte membranes depleted of spectrin and actin. Based

on its 622 amino acid composition [10-12], the predicted molecular weight of 4.1R⁸⁰ is only ~70kDa. The discrepancy between 4.1R⁸⁰ apparent (80kDa) and theoretical (70kDa) molecular weight results in part from the presence of "unstructured" domains. Limited α-chymotryptic digestion of 4.1R generates four polypeptides: a 30kDa N-terminal membrane binding domain, so-called FERM (Four.one-Ezrin-Radixin-Moesin) domain (R30), a 16kDa domain, a 10kDa spectrin-actin binding (SAB) domain and a 22/24kDa C-terminal domain (Reviewed in Refs 1-9) (Fig.1A). A 4.1R isoform expressed in erythroblasts, but not in mature erythrocytes, contains an extra N-terminal 209 amino acids headpiece (HP) region. As described above

for 4.1R⁸⁰, there is also a discrepancy between the apparent (135kDa) and theoretical (100kDa) molecular weight of this 4.1R¹³⁵ isoform. Once again, this discrepancy results at a large extent from the unstructured state of the HP region [13]. In the following, 4.1R refers to both 4.1R⁸⁰ and 4.1R¹³⁵.

Unstructured N-terminal and structured R30 of 4.1R¹³⁵

We have previously described our approach to evaluate the ordered state of various 4.1R domains [3,5]. The calculation of the disorder probability of the N-terminal HP region (RHP) and the R30 of 4.1R¹³⁵ using the PrDOS software (<http://prdos.hgc.jp/>) [14] reveals a highly disordered structure for the HP region (amino acids 1-209; disorder probability > 0.5 in the range of 0.3-0.95) that contrasts with a highly ordered structure for the R30 (amino acids 210-490; disorder probability < 0.5 in the range of 0.02-0.4), respectively (Fig.1B). A value greater than 0.5 reflects a disordered structure, with a probability of false prediction of 5% or less. Of particular note, while the overall 209 amino acid residues HP region adopts a disordered structure, a short polypeptide (amino acids 70-80), corresponding to a previously identified Ca²⁺-dependent calmodulin (CaM) binding site, S⁷⁶RGLSRLFSSFLKRPKS [15,16] (Fig.1B), adopts an ordered structure.

Figure 1 Primary structure of 4.1R isoforms and mapping of known binding partners for 4.1R. **A:** Translation of the prototypical red blood cell 80 kDa 4.1R isoform (4.1R⁸⁰) is initiated at AUG-2, which is located in exon 4. Translation of the 135 kDa 4.1R isoform (4.1R¹³⁵),

an isoform expressed in early erythroblasts and other nucleated cells, is initiated at AUG-1, which is located in exon 2' (accession ID: P11171). The 30 kDa membrane binding domain is the so-called "FERM" domain. An updated list of the binding partners identified for each domain of 4.1R is displayed. CPAP refers to a "centrosomal protein 4.1R-associated protein", reported by Hung et al. [122]. **B:** Disorder prediction for each domain has been established through the use of the PrDOS software package [14]. A disorder probability < 0.5 indicates disorder. Note that the CaM binding sequence in the HP region, S⁷⁶RGLSRLFSSFLKRPKS [15,16] is an ordered region [3].

We experimentally demonstrated that the HP is an unfolded region by SDS-PAGE, size exclusion chromatography (SEC) and dynamic light scattering (DLS)[3]. The theoretical molecular weight of RHP is 23kDa but we estimated its apparent molecular weight as 55kDa by SDS-PAGE [13]. Using DLS measurements, we calculated the hydrodynamic diameters of RHP, RHP-R30 and R30 as 7.6, 9.4 and 5.6 nm, respectively [3]. These hydrodynamic parameters enabled us to estimate the molecular weight of RHP, RHP-R30 and R30 to be 77, 127, and 40kDa, respectively. The discrepancies between theoretical and apparent molecular weights for proteins containing RHP reflect the unfolded nature of this peptide. Recently, using small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS), we demonstrated that the HP region of protein 4.1G, which contains also a 209 amino acid HP region and a FERM domain, is also an intrinsically disordered domain [17,18].

The crystal structure of 4.1R FERM domain is reminiscent of the shape of a cloverleaf or of a propeller, with three clearly distinct lobes (PDB: 1GG3) [19]. First, the N-lobe (amino acids 1-90), which corresponds to the first 90 amino acids and which includes the band 3 binding motif L³⁷EEDY, consists of 4 double-stranded β -strands. Second, the α -lobe (amino acids 91-190), which corresponds to the following 100 amino acids and which includes the glycophorin C (GPC) binding site, consists of 4 α -helices. Third, the COOH-terminal lobe (C-lobe, amino acids 191-280), which corresponds to the last 90 amino acids and which contains the p55 binding surface, consists of seven β -strands, and ends with an α -helix (Fig.2). Although numerous membrane skeletal proteins, such as human 4.1R and 4.1G, have been reported to contain intrinsically disordered (unfolded) regions, very few reports describe the function(s) of such intrinsically disordered regions [20-25]. In this respect, our findings contribute not only to a better understanding of the structure of membrane skeletal proteins but also to the function of intrinsically disordered proteins.

Expression of 4.1R¹³⁵ and 4.1R⁸⁰ in erythroblasts

In early stages of erythroblasts (CD34⁺ cells), 4.1R¹³⁵ is the only expressed 4.1R isoform, 4.1R⁸⁰ being completely absent. After the middle stage of maturation, which is reached after approximately 7 days in culture, expression of 4.1R⁸⁰ increases dramatically. In mature erythrocytes, 4.1R⁸⁰ predominates, 4.1R¹³⁵ being hardly detected by immunocytochemical methods [13,17]. The complex mechanistic regulation of 4.1R¹³⁵-4.1R⁸⁰

gene switching has been extensively described by Parra et al. [12,26-28]

Figure 2 Schematic representation of 4.1R⁸⁰ and apo-CaM. 4.1R⁸⁰ contains a FERM domain (R30), which is located at the N-terminal end and a spectrin and actin binding (SAB) domain. The R30 consists of three lobes (N-, α - and C-lobe), and adopts a three-leaf clover shape [19]. The amino terminal and carboxy terminal ends are represented as N-, α - and C-lobe. A 3D representation of apo-CaM (PDB accession ID:1dmo) and the R30 (PDB accession ID:1gg3), visualized with the MolFeat[®] software (version 4.6), is displayed.

4.1R: an essential component of the erythrocyte membrane skeleton

GPC-p55-4.1R⁸⁰ complex

GPC is a 32kDa single-transmembrane protein expressed at ~50,000-100,000 molecules/erythrocyte. The cytoplasmic domain consists of 47 amino acids (accession ID: P04921). Within this cytoplasmic domain, the R⁸²HK sequence has been identified as the 4.1R⁸⁰ binding sequence [29-39]. This RHK motif is highly conserved in the cytoplasmic domain of Neuexin IV, Paranodin and tumor suppressor lung cancer 1 (TSLC1) [40]. Girault et al. have designated this RHK motif as “GNP-motif”, to reflect its presence in the single transmembrane domain of various 4.1R binding proteins including GPC, Neuexin IV and Paranodin [39]. GPC and other GNP-motif containing proteins possess a p55-binding motif, EYFI, in their C-terminal region (Fig. 3). The dependency of proper targeting of GPC to the plasma membrane on 4.1R⁸⁰ has been demonstrated in 4.1R null mouse erythroblasts [39]. Recently, 4.1R⁸⁰ binding to GPC has been documented in trafficking vesicles in epithelial HeLa cells using fluorescence cross correlation spectroscopy [41].

Protein p55 is a 55kDa erythrocyte scaffolding protein that belongs to the membrane-associated guanylate kinase (MAGUK) family (accession ID: Q00013). This protein is characterized by the presence of a PDZ (Postsynaptic density protein-95, Dlg (*Drosophila* disc large tumor suppressor), ZO-1 (Zonula Occludens-1)) domain, a SH (src-homology) 3 domain, and a catalytic inactive guanylate kinase-like (GUK) domain, all of which function as protein-protein interaction modules [42-44]. In human

erythrocytes, p55 is expressed at ~80,000 copies per erythrocyte. p55 is also called membrane palmitoylated protein 1 (MPP1) since cysteine residues in the guanylate kinase (GUK) domain can be palmitoylated [32,44-46]. However, there is still no direct evidence for the expression of palmitoylated p55 in living cells. Although the function of p55 in erythrocytes has not been clarified, p55 seems essential for maintenance of polarity in neutrophils [45] and in hair cells [47,48]. Recently, nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (NMR)-based studies have enabled to characterize the 3D structural profile of the GPC peptide that interacts with the PDZ domain of p55 [35,38]. Mutational studies, based on the replacement of the phenylalanine residue with a cysteine residue in the EYFI motif (E¹²⁵YQ), have provided us with structural information on GPC binding to p55. We have previously shown that the p55 binding site is located in the C-lobe (exon 10-encoded region) of 4.1R⁸⁰ using resonant mirror detection [35,37]. Seo et al. reported that p55 binds to band 3 binding sequence located in the N-lobe [49]. Thus, 4.1R⁸⁰ participates in the formation of two different ternary complexes in erythrocytes, the 4.1R⁸⁰/GPC/p55 complex and the 4.1R⁸⁰/spectrin/actin complex (Fig.3).

Figure 3 Organization of the erythrocyte plasma membrane. A protein network forming a “cytoskeleton” underlies the cytoplasmic surface of the red blood cell lipid bilayer. Spectrin (α and β), actin, 4.1R and p55 are the main constituents of the skeleton. Interactions between these proteins are defined as lateral interactions. This protein network is anchored to the lipid bilayer through two vertical interactions, one involving ankyrin and band 3, the other one involving 4.1R⁸⁰, p55, and GPC. This figure does not show several additional actin-associated proteins, myosin, protein 4.9, adducin and tropomodulin and other transmembrane proteins reported by Salomao et al. [104].

band 3, NHE1 and CD44

Erythrocyte membrane stability is also controlled in part by the band 3-ankyrin-spectrin complex (Fig 3). Band 3 is a 102kDa 14-transmembrane protein which that mediates exchange of HCO₃⁻ and Cl⁻, and that is therefore referred to as anion exchanger 1 (AE1) [50-56] (accession ID:P02730). It is expressed at 1,200,000 molecules/cell. It forms dimers that assemble into tetramers, each tetramer binding to one molecule of ankyrin [2].

4.1R⁸⁰ interaction with band 3 is mediated by the L³⁷EEDY motif in the 4.1R FERM domain that binds to the I³⁸⁶RRRY and L³⁴³RRRY sequences in band 3-cytoplasmic domain ($K_d = \sim 100$ nM) [48]. Although the crystal structure of the N-terminal cytoplasmic domain of band 3 has been reported, this structure is putative as the N-terminal 55 residues, including the L³⁴³RRRY sequence, were not present in the analyzed crystal [53]. Although the results indicate that one band 3 molecule has two 4.1R⁸⁰ binding sites, the stoichiometry of band 3 binding to 4.1R⁸⁰ is still unknown. 4.1R⁸⁰ interaction with band 3 results in a decrease in ankyrin-R (red blood cell type ankyrin) binding affinity for band 3. Conversely, dissociation of 4.1R from band 3 promotes ankyrin-R binding to band 3. Thus, 4.1R⁸⁰ is able to modulate ankyrin-R binding to band 3 [54]. This competition is likely to modulate red blood cell membrane stability. In zebrafish erythrocytes, 4.1R actually binds to band 3 and mutagenesis studies have shown that proper translocation of band 3 to the plasma membrane requires 4.1R [55]. 4.1R has been also shown to regulate cell volume change of skate (*Raja erinacea*) erythrocytes, through its interaction with band 3 [56-58].

Increasing evidence indicates that 4.1R⁸⁰ acts not only in the maintenance of membrane skeletal structure but also in the regulation of the activity of some of the proteins it interacts with. Thus, we have recently demonstrated that 4.1R⁸⁰ regulates the activity of the 'housekeeping' Na⁺/H⁺ exchanger (NHE) 1 [59]. NHE1 participates in the regulation of intracellular volume and pH in almost all cell types, including erythrocytes [60-66]. 4.1R⁸⁰-null mouse erythrocytes exhibit a dramatic NHE1-dependent phenotype characterized by cell dehydration and high intracellular Na⁺ as a result of NHE1 hyperactivity [67], demonstrating unequivocally a role for 4.1R⁸⁰ in modulating NHE1 activity. We recently demonstrated that 4.1R⁸⁰ binds directly to the cytoplasmic domain of NHE1 (NHE1cd) through its FERM domain E³⁸ED motif, a motif also involved in band 3 binding (as part of the LEEDY motif), and that the E³⁸ED motif interacts with two clusters of basic amino acids in NHE1cd, K⁵¹⁹R and R⁵⁵⁶FNKKYVKK [59]. These two NHE1cd motifs have previously been shown to mediate PIP₂ (phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate) binding [59,68]. Strikingly, the affinity of 4.1R⁸⁰-NHE1cd interaction ($K_d = 100$ -200 nM) is reduced in hypertonic and acidic conditions, demonstrating that this interaction is physiologically dynamic and of electrostatic nature. The sensitivity of NHE1 - 4.1R⁸⁰ interaction to changes in tonicity and pH contrasts with the band 3 - 4.1R⁸⁰ interaction that is insensitive to such changes [59]. It is known that, when NHE1 is activated, intracellular Ca²⁺ concentration increases. Importantly, Ca²⁺/CaM decreased the affinity of the 4.1R⁸⁰ - NHE1

interaction upon binding of Ca²⁺/CaM to the 4.1R⁸⁰ FERM domain. We therefore propose that 4.1R⁸⁰ regulates NHE1 activity through a direct protein-protein interaction that can be modulated by intracellular pH as well as by intracellular Na⁺ and Ca²⁺ concentrations. In our proposed model, 4.1R⁸⁰ dissociates quickly from NHE1 when the cellular concentration of protons (H⁺) is high, i.e. when the pH is acidic. This results in an increase in NHE1 activity that mediates extrusion of the excess of H⁺ and normalization of intracellular pH. In contrast, the 4.1R⁸⁰ - band 3 interaction does not only involve electrostatic interactions between the charged EED residues in 4.1R and RRR sequences in band 3, but involves also hydrophobic residues, such as L (Leu) and I (Ile). These differences likely account for the insensitivity of the 4.1R⁸⁰ - band 3 interaction to tonicity and pH.

4.1R⁸⁰ binds to the hyaluronic acid receptor, CD44, through the C-lobe of the R30 [69-75]. Distinct regions in the cytoplasmic domain of CD44 interact with 4.1R⁸⁰ and ankyrin-R, respectively [76,77]. Preincubation of either full length 4.1R⁸⁰ or R30 with recombinant cytoplasmic domain of CD44 impairs ankyrin-R binding to the cytoplasmic domain of CD44. CD44 binds strongly to hyaluronic acid through interaction with ankyrin-R [76,77]. These results indicate that, although 4.1R⁸⁰ does not bind to the same site than ankyrin-R in the cytoplasmic domain of CD44, 4.1R⁸⁰ is able to compete with ankyrin-R and may thus modulate ankyrin-R interaction with CD44 [69,73]. The biological significance of 4.1R⁸⁰-CD44 interaction is important for tumor suppression in nucleated cells but its role in erythrocytes has not been elucidated yet [69,73].

phospholipids

Interactions of 4.1R⁸⁰ with phospholipids, phosphatidylserine (PS) and phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate (PIP₂) have been reported [78-83].

The biological significance of PS binding to 4.1R⁸⁰ is still unclear. However, the observation that the interaction between PS and 4.1R⁸⁰ is disrupted by phospholipase A₂, an enzyme whose activity is activated upon increase in intracellular Ca²⁺ concentration, provides insights into various Ca²⁺-dependent mechanisms of regulation of 4.1R⁸⁰ interaction with selected binding partners. 4.1R⁸⁰ could provide an anchor for PS in the inner leaflet of the bilayer. In functional erythrocytes, PS is indeed actively maintained in the inner leaflet of the bilayer by enzymes, such as flippase, whose activity depends on ATP [84-88]. ATP depletion in senescent erythrocytes triggers their clearance, a phenomenon known as eryptosis [89,90]. Indeed, exposure of PS on the extracellular side of the plasma membrane is a phagocytic signal for macrophages [91-94]. Upon activation of phospholipase A₂ (i.e. successive increases in intracellular Ca²⁺ concentration during the lifespan of the erythrocyte), the bond between

PS and 4.1R⁸⁰ could be broken, facilitating exposure of PS on the outer leaflet. Another important consequence of the disruption of the PS-4.1R⁸⁰ interaction could be a decrease in 4.1R⁸⁰ interaction with transmembrane proteins. Indeed, upon hydrolysis of PS by phospholipase A₂, the acyl chain released by PS remains bound to 4.1R⁸⁰. Strikingly, the resulting “acylated” 4.1R⁸⁰ can no longer interact with transmembrane proteins, such as GPC or band 3, a phenotype that is predicted to compromise erythrocyte mechanical properties and target them for clearance in the erythrocytes.

Regulation of 4.1R⁸⁰ interaction with transmembrane proteins is also regulated by PIP₂. Thus, the binding of 4.1R⁸⁰ to GPC and band 3 is enhanced and inhibited, respectively, by PIP₂ [29,81]. Our recent characterization of the interaction of 4.1R⁸⁰ with NHE1 and the opposite effect of PIP₂ and 4.1R⁸⁰ on NHE1 activity brings further credence to the important structural and regulatory functions that 4.1R⁸⁰-phospholipids may play [59,67]. The biological function of PIP₂ with other members of the protein 4.1R family, including ezrin and radixin, has also been documented not unclear, The PIP₂ binding sites in 4.1R⁸⁰ have been identified as unique tandem lysine residues in the R30, K⁶⁵K and K²⁶⁵K, based on the 3D structural analysis of a complex between PIP₃ and radixin [81,82].

spectrin-actin-4.1R⁸⁰ complex

Ektacytometry studies have revealed that 4.1R⁸⁰ plays a key role in controlling erythrocyte membrane mechanical properties. Indeed, resealed membranes, prepared from erythrocytes totally or partially deficient in 4.1R⁸⁰, show a dramatic decrease in membrane stability [1,2]. Interestingly, addition of either purified 4.1R⁸⁰ or purified 10kDa spectrin-actin binding domain of 4.1R⁸⁰ to unstable 4.1R-deficient membranes is able to restore mechanical stability to such membranes. In 4.1R⁸⁰ null erythrocytes, the membrane stability is dramatically decreased, the addition of recombinant 10kDa protein to erythrocyte membranes enabling recovery of their stability [95-99]. This demonstrates unequivocally an essential role for 4.1R⁸⁰, and more specifically for a 21 amino acid peptide encoded by exon 16 in the spectrin-actin binding domain, in maintaining membrane stability by promoting spectrin/actin interactions [95-99]. Thus, the most important function of 4.1R⁸⁰ in maintaining the mechanical stability of the erythrocyte membrane is the formation of a complex with actin and spectrin, the 4.1R 10 kDa domain containing spectrin and actin binding sites (Fig.1A) [1,2].

The absence of 4.1R, ankyrin, or spectrin or selected mutations in these three proteins all result in alterations in erythrocyte shape and mechanical properties [1,2]. The function of 4.1R has been inferred from the hematopoietic phenotype observed in human 4.1R-deficient patients, in

transgenic 4.1R knock out mice and in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) subjected to chemical mutagenesis [100,101]. We have demonstrated that 4.1R interacts with membrane protein analogues in zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) using *in vitro* binding assays [55,101-103] (accession ID: NP_778259). 4.1R deficiency leads to hereditary elliptocytosis, erythrocytes losing their typical biconcave disc shape to become elliptical. Salomao *et al.* have documented that protein 4.1R⁸⁰ can bind *in vitro* to additional erythrocyte transmembrane proteins, such as Kell, XK, Rh and Duffy [104]. These interactions remain to be validated *in vivo*. Thus, 4.1R acts in concert with an increasing list of membrane proteins for maintaining normal erythrocyte shape and function [1].

Ca²⁺/CaM-dependent regulation of 4.1R⁸⁰ interactions with membrane proteins

Binding profiles of 4.1R¹³⁵ and 4.1R⁸⁰ to membrane proteins and to CaM differ

Previous studies have shown that, while 4.1R⁸⁰ binds to both band 3 and GPC in native IOVs, it binds only to GPC in trypsinized IOVs [54]. Scatchard analysis indicates an apparent dissociation constant at equilibrium, *K'*, of 76 nM for 4.1R⁸⁰ binding to trypsinized IOVs (i.e to GPC). In contrast, *K'* for 4.1R⁸⁰ binding to native IOVs (i.e to both GPC and band 3) reaches 340 nM. A similar analysis for 4.1R¹³⁵ revealed that 4.1R¹³⁵ binding to trypsinized IOVs (i.e to GPC) is markedly weaker (*K'* of ~2 μM) than that of 4.1R⁸⁰. In contrast, *K'* for 4.1R¹³⁵ binding to native IOVs is 230 nM, similar to that observed for 4.1R⁸⁰. These findings imply that the presence or absence of the HP region in 4.1R isoforms modulates their binding affinity for GPC but not for band 3 [13].

In order to obtain independent confirmation of the binding affinities of 4.1R¹³⁵ to band 3 and GPC, we used the IAsys system-based resonant mirror detection method [13]. In agreement with the binding data using IOVs described above, there was a dramatic difference in the binding affinity of 4.1R¹³⁵ to band 3 and GPC, the binding affinity being much higher for band 3 (23 ± 2 nM) than for GPC (1327 ± 103 nM). In marked contrast, *K_d* values for binding of 4.1R⁸⁰ to both band 3 and GPC were very similar, in the sub-micro molar range. This confirmed an important role for the HP region in regulating 4.1R affinities for its two major transmembrane binding partners. In contrast to the marked differences in the binding affinities of 4.1R¹³⁵ and 4.1R⁸⁰ to band 3 and GPC, the two isoforms bound to p55 with very similar affinities, in the sub-micro molar range.

As expected from the data obtained with 4.1R⁸⁰ and 4.1R¹³⁵ isoforms, the addition of RHP to R30 (RHP-R30) results in a profound change in the ability of R30 to bind to band 3 and GPC. Indeed, the binding affinity of RHP-R30 for band 3 is 35-fold higher than for GPC. Together, these findings

highlight an important role for the RHP in modulating the interaction of the R30 with its two membrane binding partners, GPC and band 3.

Differences in CaM binding to 4.1R isoforms

We and other groups have previously documented that 4.1R⁸⁰ binds to CaM with a K_d in the submicromolar range, both in the presence and absence of Ca²⁺, implying that this interaction is Ca²⁺-independent [105-109]. We have also examined the nature of the interaction between 4.1R¹³⁵ and CaM. Kinetic analysis of 4.1R¹³⁵ interaction with CaM using the IAsys system identified a very strong interaction with a K_d of 51±5 nM in the presence of Ca²⁺. In the absence of Ca²⁺, the binding affinity decreased by over 100-fold. Thus, in contrast to 4.1R⁸⁰, the interaction of 4.1R¹³⁵ with CaM is strongly Ca²⁺-dependent. Probing of the HP region alone confirms a Ca²⁺-dependent interaction with CaM, implying that this region harbors the Ca²⁺-dependent CaM binding site [13,108]. Our observations are in accordance with Leclerc and Vetter's study that identifies the S⁷⁶RGLSRLFSSFLKRPKS peptide as the Ca²⁺-dependent CaM binding sequence in the RHP region [16]. The stoichiometry of 4.1R¹³⁵ binding to CaM in the presence of Ca²⁺ is 1:1 as assessed by quartz crystal microbalance (QCM) method [13]. Together, these results support that Ca²⁺/CaM binds to the HP region but not to the 30kDa domain of 4.1R¹³⁵ [13].

Regulation of 4.1R¹³⁵ interactions with membrane proteins by Ca²⁺/CaM

The binding affinity of 4.1R¹³⁵ for band 3 N-terminal cytoplasmic domain is decreased by almost 2 orders of magnitude by Ca²⁺/CaM. Moreover, Ca²⁺/CaM completely abolishes the ability of 4.1R¹³⁵ to bind to either GPC or p55. Either 5 μM CaM or 100 μM Ca²⁺ alone has no effect on binding affinities. 4.1R¹³⁵ binding to band 3 N-terminal cytoplasmic domain starts to decline at [Ca²⁺]_i greater than 10 nM ($pCa < 8$) with a maximal inhibition at 100 μM ($pCa > 4$). Half maximal binding is observed at a [Ca²⁺]_i of 3.2 μM ($pCa = 5.5$). In the case of 4.1R⁸⁰, Ca²⁺/CaM binding to the R30 reduces about 10 times the binding affinity for band 3. Thus, we noted significant differences between 4.1R¹³⁵ and 4.1R⁸⁰ in the Ca²⁺-dependence for the binding of these two isoforms to CaM. In contrast to the Ca²⁺-independent binding of CaM to 4.1R⁸⁰, CaM binding to 4.1R¹³⁵ is strongly Ca²⁺-dependent. This difference is once again directly attributable to the HP region present in 4.1R¹³⁵. Importantly, in contrast to band 3 and GPC, that do not directly bind to the RHP, this region by itself binds to CaM in a Ca²⁺-dependent manner. Thus, it must be inferred that the CaM binding site in the RHP is the dominant binding site for CaM in 4.1R¹³⁵ and that this site

prevents the binding of CaM to the Ca²⁺-independent binding site identified in 4.1R⁸⁰. Furthermore, our finding that CaM dramatically decreases the binding of 4.1R¹³⁵ to band 3 in a Ca²⁺-dependent manner and abolishes 4.1R¹³⁵ binding to GPC and p55 has implications for the function of this 4.1R isoform in early erythroblasts. Indeed, while low levels of Ca²⁺ in early erythroblasts will lead to membrane association of 4.1R¹³⁵ through high affinity interaction with band 3, increasing levels of Ca²⁺ occurring during erythroid differentiation will lead to the displacement of 4.1R¹³⁵ from the membrane and to a possible subsequent degradation and loss of this isoform from erythroblasts. Our findings that a fraction of 4.1R¹³⁵ is associated with the membrane of early erythroblasts and that erythroblasts cultured in presence of 1 mM EGTA (a chelator of Ca²⁺) exhibit sustained expression of 4.1R¹³⁵ at or near the plasma membrane compared to non-treated erythroblasts lends support to this hypothesis [13]. Precise quantitative measurements of intracellular Ca²⁺ levels in erythroblasts at different stages of maturation need to be performed to validate further this hypothesis [110-112].

4.1R requires apo-CaM for structural stability

apo-CaM binding to 4.1R⁸⁰

CaM binding to or dissociation from its target proteins is generally strongly dependent on intracellular Ca²⁺ concentration [113-118]. As stated above, human 4.1R⁸⁰ binds to CaM in a Ca²⁺-independent manner [108], an unusual feature that typifies 4.1R among CaM binding proteins. The biological significance of this interaction has been unclear until recently. We have mapped the CaM binding sites in 4.1R. *In vitro* protein binding assays enabled us to identify two distinct CaM binding sites within the R30: a Ca²⁺-insensitive binding site, A²⁶⁴KKLWKCVEHHTFFRL, encoded by exon 11 (pep11), and a Ca²⁺-sensitive binding site, mediated by Ser¹⁸⁵ in the A¹⁸¹KKLSMYGVDLHKAKD sequence, encoded by exon 9 (pep9) [108]. We compared the characteristics of pep11 binding to CaM in absence of Ca²⁺ (apo-CaM) and to Ca²⁺-saturated CaM (Ca²⁺/CaM) [109,119]. The pep 11 bound only to the C-lobe of apo-CaM but to both N- and C-lobes in Ca²⁺/CaM. We then investigated the consequences of CaM binding to R30 on R30 structural stability using the IAsys biosensor and Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy. After a 30 min incubation above 40°C, R30 could no longer bind to band 3 nor to GPC. In contrast, R30 could still bind to p55, binding being detectable at a temperature as low as 34°C and as high as 44°C, in the presence of apo-CaM. However, in the presence of Ca²⁺, CaM inhibited binding of R30 to p55 at 34°C. We verified by DLS measurements that R30, either alone or complexed with apo-CaM, did not aggregate up to 40°C. FT-IR spectroscopy

revealed that the dramatic variations in the structure of the β -sheet structure of R30 observed at various temperatures were minimized in the presence of apo-CaM. On the basis of K_d values calculated at various temperatures, ΔC_p and ΔG° for R30 binding to apo-CaM were determined as $-10 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ and $\sim -38 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ at 37°C (310.15 K), respectively. These data support that apo-CaM stabilizes R30 through interaction with its β -strand-rich C-lobe and suggest a novel function for CaM, i.e. structural stabilization of 4.1R⁸⁰ [109].

Structural stabilization of CaM by 4.1R⁸⁰ binding

Using biophysical, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and NMR approaches, we investigated the characteristics of the pep11 binding site and the profiles of CaM in the presence and absence of Ca^{2+} [119]. DSC analysis revealed that the thermostability of CaM was increased upon pep11 binding independently of Ca^{2+} . This analysis also showed that the C-lobe of CaM was more stable when bound to pep11 either in the presence or absence of Ca^{2+} . Using NMR, we identified 8 residues in the N-lobe and 14 residues in the C-lobe of pep11 involved in pep11 interaction with CaM in both presence and absence of Ca^{2+} . Finally, the generation of Kratky plots by SAXS analysis demonstrated that the pep11/ Ca^{2+} /CaM complex adopted a relaxed globular shape. We propose that these unique properties may account in part for the previously described Ca^{2+} /CaM-dependent regulation of R30 binding to membrane proteins.

Evolutionary changes of 4.1R-CaM binding sites

Chaperon-like functions, such as the ones proposed here for CaM and 4.1R, are not only seen in human but also in zebra fish (*Danio rerio*). Indeed, we have shown that, as seen in human, CaM also binds to 4.1R⁸⁰ in a Ca^{2+} -independent manner in zebra fish. However, the regulatory role of CaM in zebra fish is more limited since, unlike in human, Ca^{2+} /CaM does not appear to regulate 4.1R binding to GPC, band 3 and p55 [102]. This may be explained by differences in amino acid sequence. Indeed, the key serine residue for Ca^{2+} /CaM-dependent regulation of human 4.1R⁸⁰ binding to membrane proteins, Ser¹⁸⁵ in the exon 9-encoded region of human 4.1R, is replaced with an alanine residue in zebra fish 4.1R [102]. Such mutation events may represent important gains of function selected upon evolution towards organisms with increased complexity and specialization.

Conclusion and Future Studies on CaM and 4.1R

This review describes the structure and function of the N-terminal intrinsically disordered RHP and structured R30, and the role of Ca^{2+} in regulating 4.1R isoforms binding to membrane proteins through CaM. Our findings are based on *in vitro* binding assays. Direct evidence for these interactions and their regulations in living cells remain to be

established. Although it is known that the RHP contains phosphorylation sites [120], the relationship between Ca^{2+} /CaM regulation and phosphorylation remains also to be investigated.

Taken together, our results support the concept that CaM and 4.1R⁸⁰ both function as chaperon-like proteins and that they mutually fulfill this function for each other. We propose that such interactions may participate in protein stabilization over the 120-day lifespan of human erythrocytes and that these protective mechanisms may compensate for the lack of protein synthesis (replenishment) in such terminally differentiated enucleated cells. Maintaining the structure and function of proteins with key regulatory functions, such as CaM with respect to regulation of Ca^{2+} -ATPase, is paramount. The mechanisms that participate in CaM dissociation from 4.1R⁸⁰, including dynamic changes in protein 4.1R⁸⁰ phosphorylation and interaction with lipids, as well as the effects of CaM silencing on erythrocyte biology remain to be further investigated *in vivo* [121]. The information gained will provide us with novel insights about the chaperon-like function of CaM and 4.1R⁸⁰ in mammalian erythrocytes.

Acknowledgments

We thank Dr. Philippe Gascard (University of California at San Francisco, San Francisco, CA, USA) for evaluation and editing of the manuscript.

References

- Baines AJ, Lu HC, Bennett PM (2014). The Protein 4.1 family: Hub proteins in animals for organizing membrane proteins. *Biochim Biophys Acta*, 1838: 605-619.
- Bennett V, Baines AJ (2001). Spectrin and ankyrin-based pathways: metazoan inventions for integrating cells into tissues. *Physiol Rev*, 81: 1353-1392.
- Nunomura W, Gascard P, Takakuwa Y (2011). Insights into the function of the unstructured N-terminal domain of proteins 4.1R and 4.1G in erythropoiesis. *Int J Cell Biol*, 2011: 943272.
- Diakowski W, Grzybek M, Sikorski AF (2006). Protein 4.1, a component of the erythrocyte membrane skeleton and its related homologue proteins forming the protein 4.1/FERM superfamily. *Folia Histochem Cytobiol*, 44: 231-248.
- Nunomura W, Takakuwa Y (2006). Regulation of protein 4.1R interactions with membrane proteins by Ca^{2+} and calmodulin. *Front Biosci*, 11: 1522-1539.
- Baines AJ (2006). A FERM-adjacent (FA) region defines a subset of the 4.1 superfamily and is a potential regulator of FERM domain function. *BMC Genomics*, 7: 85.
- Nunomura W, Takakuwa Y (2003). Protein 4.1 as a modulator of membrane skeletal organization and function of erythrocyte. *Recent Res Dev Cell Res*, 1:67-76.
- Nunomura W (2001). Regulation of protein 4.1 interactions by Ca^{2+} and calmodulin: insights into dynamic organization of the membrane skeleton viewed as a complex system. *Res Adv Biol Chem*, 1:25-49.
- Takakuwa Y (2000). Protein 4.1, a multifunctional protein of the erythrocyte membrane skeleton: structure and functions in erythrocytes and nonerythroid cells. *Int J Hematol*, 72: 298-309.
- Conboy J, Kan YW, Shohet SB, Mohandas N (1986). Molecular cloning of protein 4.1, a major structural element of the human erythrocyte membrane skeleton. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 83: 9512-9516.
- Conboy JG, Chan J, Mohandas N, Kan YW (1988). Multiple protein 4.1 isoforms produced by alternative splicing in human erythroid cells. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 85:9062-9065.
- Gascard P, Lee G, Coulombel L, Auffray I, Lum M, et al. (1998). Characterization of multiple isoforms of protein 4.1R expressed during erythroid terminal differentiation. *Blood*, 92: 4404-4414.

13. Nunomura W, Parra M, Hebiguchi M, Sawada K, Mohandas N, *et al.* (2009). Marked difference in membrane-protein-binding properties of the two isoforms of protein 4.1R expressed at early and late stages of erythroid differentiation. *Biochem J*, 417: 141-148.
14. Ishida T, Kinoshita K (2007). PrDOS: prediction of disordered protein regions from amino acid sequence. *Nucleic Acids Res*, 35: W460-464.
15. Kelly GM, Zelus BD, Moon RT (1991). Identification of a calcium-dependent calmodulin-binding domain in *Xenopus* membrane skeleton protein 4.1. *J Biol Chem*, 266: 12469-12473.
16. Leclerc E, Vetter S (1998). Characterization of a calcium-dependent calmodulin-binding domain in the 135-kD human protein 4.1 isoform. *Eur J Biochem*, 258: 567-571.
17. Nunomura W, Kinoshita K, Parra M, Gascard P, An X, *et al.* (2010). Similarities and differences in the structure and function of 4.1G and 4.1R¹³⁵, two protein 4.1 paralogues expressed in erythroid cells. *Biochem J*, 432: 407-416.
18. Nunomura W, Jinbo Y, Isozumi N, Ohki S, Izumi Y, *et al.* (2013). Novel mechanism of regulation of protein 4.1G binding properties through Ca²⁺/calmodulin-mediated structural changes. *Cell Biochem Biophys*, 66: 545-558.
19. Han BG, Nunomura W, Takakuwa Y, Mohandas N, Jap BK (2000). Protein 4.1R core domain structure and insights into regulation of cytoskeletal organization. *Nat Struct Biol*, 7: 871-875.
20. Eliezer D (2009). Biophysical characterization of intrinsically disordered proteins. *Curr Opin Struct Biol*, 19: 23-30.
21. Espinoza-Fonseca LM (2009). Reconciling binding mechanisms of intrinsically disordered proteins. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun*, 382: 479-482.
22. Dunker AK, Cortese MS, Romero P, Iakoucheva LM, Uversky VN (2005). Flexible nets: The roles of intrinsic disorder in protein interaction networks. *FEBS J*, 272:5129-5148.
23. Minezaki Y, Homma K, Nishikawa K (2007). Intrinsically disordered regions of human plasma membrane proteins preferentially occur in the cytoplasmic segment. *J Mol Biol*, 368: 902-913.
24. Sigalov AB (2010). Membrane binding of intrinsically disordered proteins: Critical importance of an appropriate membrane model. *Self Nonself*, 1: 129-132.
25. Nørholm AB, Hendus-Altenburger R, Bjerre G, Kjaergaard M, Pedersen SF, *et al.* (2011). The intracellular distal tail of the Na⁺/H⁺ exchanger NHE1 is intrinsically disordered: implications for NHE1 trafficking. *Biochemistry*, 50: 3469-3480.
26. Parra MK, Tan JS, Mohandas N, Conboy JG (2008). Intrasplicing coordinates alternative first exons with alternative splicing in the protein 4.1R gene. *EMBO J*, 27:122-131.
27. Parra MK, Gee S, Mohandas N, Conboy JG (2011). Efficient in vivo manipulation of alternative pre-mRNA splicing events using antisense morpholinos in mice. *J Biol Chem*, 286:6033-6039.
28. Parra MK, Gallagher TL, Amacher SL, Mohandas N, Conboy JG (2012). Deep bintron elements mediate nested splicing events at consecutive AG dinucleotides to regulate alternative 3' splice site choice in vertebrate 4.1 genes. *Mol Cell Biol*, 32:2044-2053.
29. Anderson RA, Lovrien RE (1984). Glycophorin is linked by band 4.1 protein to the human erythrocyte membrane skeleton. *Nature*, 307(5952): 655-658.
30. Hemming NJ, Anstee DJ, Mawby WJ, Reid ME, Tanner MJ (1994). Localization of the protein 4.1-binding site on human erythrocyte glycophorins C and D. *Biochem J*, 299:191-196.
31. Hemming NJ, Anstee DJ, Staricoff MA, Tanner MJ, Mohandas N (1995). Identification of the membrane attachment sites for protein 4.1 in the human erythrocyte. *J Biol Chem*, 270: 5360-5366.
32. Marfatia SM, Leu RA, Branton D, Chishti AH (1995). Identification of the protein 4.1 binding interface on glycophorin C and p55, a homologue of the *Drosophila* discs-large tumor suppressor protein. *J Biol Chem*, 270: 715-719.
33. Marfatia SM, Morais-Cabral JH, Kim AC, Byron O, Chishti AH (1997). The PDZ domain of human erythrocyte p55 mediates its binding to the cytoplasmic carboxyl terminus of glycophorin C. Analysis of the binding interface by in vitro mutagenesis. *J Biol Chem*, 272: 24191-24197.
34. Nunomura W, Takakuwa Y, Parra M, Conboy J, Mohandas N (2000). Regulation of protein 4.1R, p55, and glycophorin C ternary complex in human erythrocyte membrane. *J Biol Chem*, 275: 24540-24546.
35. Kusunoki H, Kohno T (2007). Structural insight into the interaction between the p55 PDZ domain and glycophorin C. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun*, 359: 972-978.
36. Hoover KB, Bryant PJ (2000). The genetics of the protein 4.1 family: organizers of the membrane and cytoskeleton. *Curr Opin Cell Biol*, 12: 229-234.
37. Nunomura W, Hatakeyama M, Takakuwa Y (2012). Characterization of mouse monoclonal antibodies to human protein 4.1R FERM Domain : Epitope mapping and application to FERM domain binding to red blood cell inside-out vesicles. *Membrane*, 37:250-257.
38. Kusunoki H, Kohno T (2009). Solution structure and glycophorin C binding studies of the protein 4.1R FERM alpha-lobe domain. *Proteins*, 76: 255-260.
39. Salomao M, Chen K, Villalobos J, Mohandas N, An X, *et al.* (2010). Hereditary spherocytosis and hereditary elliptocytosis: aberrant protein sorting during erythroblast enucleation. *Blood*, 116: 267-269.
40. Yageta M, Kuramochi M, Masuda M, Fukami T, Fukuhara H, *et al.* (2002). Direct association of TSLC1 and DAL-1, two distinct tumor suppressor proteins in lung cancer. *Cancer Res*, 62: 5129-5133.
41. Tanaka S, Takakuwa Y (2012). Intracellular interactions between protein 4.1 and glycophorin C on transport vesicles, as determined by fluorescence correlation spectroscopy. *FEBS Lett*, 586: 668-674.
42. Biernatowska A, Podkalicka J, Majkowski M, Hryniewicz-Jankowska A, Augoff K, *et al.* (2013). The role of MPP1/p55 and its palmitoylation in resting state raft organization in HEL cells. *Biochim Biophys Acta*, 1833: 1876-1884.
43. Lach A, Grzybek M, Heger E, Korycka J, Wolny M, *et al.* (2012). Palmitoylation of MPP1 (membrane-palmitoylated protein 1)/p55 is crucial for lateral membrane organization in erythroid cells. *J Biol Chem*, 287: 18974-18984.
44. Dimitratos SD, Woods DF, Stathakis DG, Bryant PJ (1999). Signaling pathways are focused at specialized regions of the plasma membrane by scaffolding proteins of the MAGUK family. *Bioessays*, 21: 912-921.
45. Quinn BJ, Welch EJ, Kim AC, Lokuta MA, Huttenlocher A, *et al.* (2009). Erythrocyte scaffolding protein p55/MPP1 functions as an essential regulator of neutrophil polarity. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 106: 19842-19847.
46. Charollais J, Van Der Goot FG (2009). Palmitoylation of membrane proteins (Review). *Mol Membr Biol*, 26: 55-66.
47. Mburu P, Kikkawa Y, Townsend S, Romero R, Yonekawa H, *et al.* (2006). Whirlin complexes with p55 at the stereocilia tip during hair cell development. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 103: 10973-10978.
48. Mburu P, Romero MR, Hilton H, Parker A, Townsend S, *et al.* (2010). Gelsolin plays a role in the actin polymerization complex of hair cell stereocilia. *PLoS One*, 5: e11627.
49. Seo PS, Jeong JJ, Zeng L, Takoudis CG, Quinn BJ, *et al.* (2009). Alternatively spliced exon 5 of the FERM domain of protein 4.1R encodes a novel binding site for erythrocyte p55 and is critical for membrane targeting in epithelial cells. *Biochim Biophys Acta*, 1793: 281-289.
50. Pasternack GR, Anderson RA, Leto TL, Marchesi VT (1985). Interactions between protein 4.1 and band 3. An alternative binding site for an element of the membrane skeleton. *J Biol Chem*, 260: 3676-3683.
51. Michaely P, Bennett V (1995). The ANK repeats of erythrocyte ankyrin form two distinct but cooperative binding sites for the erythrocyte anion exchanger. *J Biol Chem*, 270: 22050-22057.
52. Jöns T, Drenckhahn D (1992). Identification of the binding interface involved in linkage of cytoskeletal protein 4.1 to the erythrocyte anion exchanger. *EMBO J*, 11: 2863-2867.
53. Zhang D, Kiyatkin A, Bolin JT, Low PS (2000). Crystallographic structure and functional interpretation of the cytoplasmic domain of erythrocyte membrane band 3. *Blood*, 96: 2925-2933.
54. An XL, Takakuwa Y, Nunomura W, Manno S, Mohandas N (1996). Modulation of band 3-ankyrin interaction by protein 4.1. Functional implications in regulation of erythrocyte membrane mechanical properties. *J Biol Chem*, 271: 33187-33191.
55. Paw BH, Davidson AJ, Zhou Y, Li R, Pratt SJ, *et al.* (2003). Cell-specific mitotic defect and dyserythropoiesis associated with erythroid band 3 deficiency. *Nat Genet*, 34: 59-64.
56. Musch MW, Goldstein L (2001). Modulation of erythrocyte band 4.1 binding by volume expansion. *J Exp Zool*, 289: 177-183.
57. Perlman DF, Musch MW, Goldstein L (1996). Band 3 in cell volume regulation in fish erythrocytes. *Cell Mol Biol (Noisy-le-grand)*, 42: 975-984.
58. Perlman DF, Musch MW, Goldstein L (2006). Cell membrane surface expression and tyrosine kinase regulate the osmolyte channel (skAE1) in skate erythrocytes. *Acta Physiol (Oxf)*, 187: 87-91.
59. Nunomura W, Denker SP, Barber DL, Takakuwa Y, Gascard P (2012). Characterization of cytoskeletal protein 4.1R interaction with NHE1 (Na⁺/H⁺ exchanger isoform 1). *Biochem J*, 446: 427-435.
60. Sarangarajan R, Dhabia N, Soleimani M, Baird N, Joiner C (1998). NHE-1 is the sodium-hydrogen exchanger isoform present in erythroid cells. *Biochim Biophys Acta*, 1374: 56-62.
61. Slepov E, Fliegel L (2002). Structure and function of the NHE1 isoform of the Na⁺/H⁺ exchanger. *Biochem Cell Biol*, 80: 499-508.

62. Denker SP, Barber DL (2002). Ion transport proteins anchor and regulate the cytoskeleton. *Curr Opin Cell Biol*, 14: 214-220.
63. Orłowski J, Grinstein S (2004). Diversity of the mammalian sodium/proton exchanger SLC9 gene family. *Pflugers Arch*, 447: 549-565.
64. Meima ME, Mackley JR, Barber DL (2007). Beyond ion translocation: structural functions of the sodium-hydrogen exchanger isoform-1. *Curr Opin Nephrol Hypertens*, 16: 365-372.
65. Stock C, Schwab A (2006). Role of the Na⁺/H⁺ exchanger NHE1 in cell migration. *Acta Physiol (Oxf)*, 187: 149-157.
66. Wooden JM, Finney GL, Rynes E, Maccoss MJ, Lambert AJ, et al. (2011). Comparative proteomics reveals deficiency of SLC9A1 (sodium/hydrogen exchanger NHE1) in β-adducin null red cells. *Br J Haematol*, 154: 492-501.
67. Rivera A, De Franceschi L, Peters LL, Gascard P, Mohandas N, et al. (2006). Effect of complete protein 4.1R deficiency on ion transport properties of murine erythrocytes. *Am J Physiol Cell Physiol*, 291: C880-886.
68. Aharonovitz O, Zaun HC, Balla T, York JD, Orłowski J, et al. (2000). Intracellular pH regulation by Na⁺/H⁺ exchange requires phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate. *J Cell Biol*, 150: 213-224.
69. Nunomura W, Takakuwa Y, Tokimitsu R, Krauss SW, Kawashima M, et al. (1997). Regulation of CD44-protein 4.1 interaction by Ca²⁺ and calmodulin. Implications for modulation of CD44-ankyrin interaction. *J Biol Chem*, 272: 30322-30328.
70. Sun CX, Robb VA, Gutmann DH (2002). Protein 4.1 tumor suppressors: getting a FERM grip on growth regulation. *J Cell Sci*, 115: 3991-4000.
71. Bourguignon LY (2001). CD44-mediated oncogenic signaling and cytoskeleton activation during mammary tumor progression. *J Mammary Gland Biol Neoplasia*, 6: 287-297.
72. Robb VA, Li W, Gascard P, Perry A, Mohandas N, et al. (2003). Identification of a third Protein 4.1 tumor suppressor, Protein 4.1R, in meningioma pathogenesis. *Neurobiol Dis*, 13: 191-202.
73. Hattori M, Nunomura W, Ito E, Ohta H, and Takakuwa Y (2006). Regulation of ankyrin interaction with CD44 by protein 4.1 in HeLa cells. *Membrane*, 31:107-114.
74. Mori T, Kitano K, Terawaki S, Maesaki R, Fukami Y, et al. (2008). Structural basis for CD44 recognition by ERM proteins. *J Biol Chem*, 283: 29602-29612.
75. Jeremy KP, Plummer ZE, Head DJ, Madgett TE, Sanders KL, Wallington A, Storry JR, Gilsanz F, Delaunay J, Avent ND (2009). 4.1R-deficient human red blood cells have altered phosphatidylserine exposure pathways and are deficient in CD44 and CD47 glycoproteins. *Haematologica*, 94:1354-1361.
76. Zhu D, Bourguignon LY (1998). The ankyrin-binding domain of CD44 is involved in regulating hyaluronic acid-mediated functions and prostate tumor cell transformation. *Cell Motil Cytoskeleton*, 39: 209-222.
77. Bourguignon LY, Zhu D, Zhu H (1998). CD44 isoform-cytoskeleton interaction in oncogenic signaling and tumor progression. *Front Biosci*, 3: d637-649.
78. Rybicki AC, Heath R, Lubin B, Schwartz RS (1988). Human erythrocyte protein 4.1 is a phosphatidylserine binding protein. *J Clin Invest*, 81: 255-260.
79. Cohen AM, Liu SC, Lawler J, Derick L, Palek J (1988). Identification of the protein 4.1 binding site to phosphatidylserine vesicles. *Biochemistry*, 27: 614-619.
80. An XL, Takakuwa Y, Manno S, Han BG, Gascard P, et al. (2001). Structural and functional characterization of protein 4.1R-phosphatidylserine interaction: potential role in 4.1R sorting within cells. *J Biol Chem*, 276: 35778-35785.
81. An X, Zhang X, Debnath G, Baines AJ, Mohandas N (2006). Phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate (PIP₂) differentially regulates the interaction of human erythrocyte protein 4.1 (4.1R) with membrane proteins. *Biochemistry*, 45: 5725-5732.
82. Hamada K, Shimizu T, Matsui T, Tsukita S, Hakoshima T (2000). Structural basis of the membrane-targeting and unmasking mechanisms of the radixin FERM domain. *EMBO J*, 19: 4449-4462.
83. Chaurio RA, Janko C, Muñoz LE, Frey B, Herrmann M, et al. (2009). Phospholipids: key players in apoptosis and immune regulation. *Molecules*, 14: 4892-4914.
84. Devaux PF (1992). Protein involvement in transmembrane lipid asymmetry. *Annu Rev Biophys Biomol Struct*, 21: 417-439.
85. Devaux PF, Morris R (2004). Transmembrane asymmetry and lateral domains in biological membranes. *Traffic*, 5: 241-246.
86. Devaux PF, Herrmann A, Ohlwein N, Kozlov MM (2008). How lipid flippases can modulate membrane structure. *Biochim Biophys Acta*, 1778: 1591-1600.
87. Manno S, Mohandas N, Takakuwa Y (2010). ATP-dependent mechanism protects spectrin against glycation in human erythrocytes. *J Biol Chem*, 285: 33923-33929.
88. Arashiki N, Kimata N, Manno S, Mohandas N, Takakuwa Y (2013). Membrane peroxidation and methemoglobin formation are both necessary for band 3 clustering: mechanistic insights into human erythrocyte senescence. *Biochemistry*, 52:5760- 5769.
89. Lang E, Qadri SM, Lang F (2012). Killing me softly - suicidal erythrocyte death. *Int J Biochem Cell Biol*, 44: 1236-1243.
90. Lang F, Qadri SM (2012). Mechanisms and significance of eryptosis, the suicidal death of erythrocytes. *Blood Purif*, 33: 125-130.
91. Burger P, de Korte D, van den Berg TK, van Bruggen R (2012). CD47 in erythrocyte ageing and clearance - the Dutch Point of View. *Transfus Med Hemother*, 39: 348-352.
92. Grimsley C, Ravichandran KS (2003). Cues for apoptotic cell engulfment: eat-me, don't eat-me and come-get-me signals. *Trends Cell Biol*, 13: 648-656.
93. Nagata S, Hanayama R, Kawane K (2010). Autoimmunity and the clearance of dead cells. *Cell*, 140: 619-630.
94. Toda S, Hanayama R, Nagata S (2012). Two-step engulfment of apoptotic cells. *Mol Cell Biol*, 32: 118-125.
95. Discher D, Parra M, Conboy JG, Mohandas N (1993). Mechanochemistry of the alternatively spliced spectrin-actin binding domain in membrane skeletal protein 4.1. *J Biol Chem*, 268: 7186-7195.
96. Discher DE, Mohandas N, Evans EA (1994). Molecular maps of red cell deformation: hidden elasticity and in situ connectivity. *Science*, 266: 1032-1035.
97. Discher DE, Winardi R, Schischmanoff PO, Parra M, Conboy JG, Mohandas N (1995). Mechanochemistry of protein 4.1's spectrin-actin-binding domain: ternary complex interactions, membrane binding, network integration, structural strengthening. *J Cell Biol*, 130:897-907.
98. Schischmanoff PO, Winardi R, Discher DE, Parra MK, Bicknese SE, et al. (1995). Defining of the minimal domain of protein 4.1 involved in spectrin-actin binding. *J Biol Chem*, 270: 21243-21250.
99. Gimm JA, An X, Nunomura W, Mohandas N (2002). Functional characterization of spectrin-actin-binding domains in 4.1 family of proteins. *Biochemistry*, 41: 7275-7282.
100. Shi ZT, Afzal V, Coller B, Patel D, Chasis JA, et al. (1999). Protein 4.1R-deficient mice are viable but have erythroid membrane skeleton abnormalities. *J Clin Invest*, 103: 331-340.
101. Shafizadeh E, Paw BH, Foott H, Liao EC, Barut BA, et al. (2002). Characterization of zebrafish merlot/chablis as non-mammalian vertebrate models for severe congenital anemia due to protein 4.1 deficiency. *Development*, 129: 4359-4370.
102. Nunomura W, Takakuwa Y, Cherr GN, Murata K (2007). Characterization of protein 4.1R in erythrocytes of zebrafish (*Danio rerio*): unique binding properties with transmembrane proteins and calmodulin. *Comp Biochem Physiol B Biochem Mol Biol*, 148:124-138.
103. Murata K, Nunomura W, Takakuwa Y, Cherr GN (2010). Two different unique cardiac isoforms of protein 4.1R in zebrafish, *Danio rerio*, and insights into their cardiac functions as related to their unique structures. *Dev Growth Differ*, 52: 591-602.
104. Salomao M, Zhang X, Yang Y, Lee S, Hartwig JH, et al. (2008). Protein 4.1R-dependent multiprotein complex: new insights into the structural organization of the red blood cell membrane. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA*, 105: 8026-8031.
105. Takakuwa Y, Mohandas N (1988). Modulation of erythrocyte membrane material properties by Ca²⁺ and calmodulin. Implications for their role in regulation of skeletal protein interactions. *J Clin Invest*, 82: 394-400.
106. Tanaka T, Kadowaki K, Lazarides E, Sobue K (1991). Ca²⁺-dependent regulation of the spectrin/actin interaction by calmodulin and protein 4.1. *J Biol Chem*, 266: 1134-1140.
107. Lombardo CR, Low PS (1994). Calmodulin modulates protein 4.1 binding to human erythrocyte membranes. *Biochim Biophys Acta*, 1196: 139-144.
108. Nunomura W, Takakuwa Y, Parra M, Conboy JG, Mohandas N (2000). Ca²⁺-dependent and Ca²⁺-independent calmodulin binding sites in erythrocyte protein 4.1. Implications for regulation of protein 4.1 interactions with transmembrane proteins. *J Biol Chem*, 275: 6360-6367.
109. Nunomura W, Sasakura D, Shiba K, Nakamura S, Kidokoro S, Takakuwa Y (2011). Structural stabilization of protein 4.1R FERM domain upon binding to apo-calmodulin: novel insights into the biological significance of the calcium-independent binding of calmodulin to protein 4.1R. *Biochem J*, 440:367-374.
110. Bogdanova A, Makhro A, Wang J, Lipp P, Kaestner L (2013). Calcium in red blood cells-a perilous balance. *Int J Mol Sci*, 14: 9848-9872.
111. Yelamarty RV, Miller BA, Scaduto Jr RC, Yu FTS, Tillotson DL, Cheung JY (1990). Three-dimensional intracellular gradients in single human burst-forming units-erythroid-derived erythroblasts induced by erythropoietin. *J Clin Invest*, 85:1799-1809.
112. Miller BA, Scaduto RC Jr, Tillotson DL, Botti JJ, Cheung JY (1988). Erythropoietin stimulates a rise in intracellular free calcium

- concentration in single early human erythroid precursors. *J Clin Invest*, 82: 309-315.
113. Jurado LA, Chockalingam PS, Jarrett HW (1999). Apocalmodulin. *Physiol Rev*, 79: 661-682.
114. Hoeflich KP, Ikura M (2002). Calmodulin in action: diversity in target recognition and activation mechanisms. *Cell*, 108: 739-742.
115. Ishida H, and Vogel HJ (2006). Protein-peptide interaction studies demonstrate the versatility of calmodulin target protein binding. *Protein Pep Lett*, 13:455-465.
116. Gifford JL, Walsh MP, Vogel HJ (2007). Structures and metal-ion-binding properties of the Ca²⁺-binding helix-loop-helix EF-hand motifs. *Biochem J*, 405: 199-221.
117. Rhoads AR, Friedberg F (1997). Sequence motifs for calmodulin recognition. *FASEB J*, 11: 331-340.
118. Yap KL, Kim J, Truong K, Sherman M, Yuan T, et al. (2000). Calmodulin target database. *J Struct Funct Genomics*, 1: 8-14.
119. Nunomura W, Isozumi N, Jinbo Y, Ohki S, Kidokoro S, Wakui H, Takakuwa Y (2013). Unique structural changes in calcium-bound calmodulin upon interaction with protein 4.1R FERM domain: novel insights into the calcium-dependent regulation of 4.1R FERM domain binding to membrane proteins by calmodulin. *Cell Biochem Biophys*, in press DOI:10.1007/s12013-012-9502-7.
120. Huang SC, Liu ES, Chan SH, Munagala ID, Cho HT, et al. (2005). Mitotic regulation of protein 4.1R involves phosphorylation by cdc2 kinase. *Mol Biol Cell*, 16: 117-127.
121. Manno S, Takakuwa Y, Mohandas N (2005). Modulation of erythrocyte membrane mechanical function by protein 4.1 phosphorylation. *J Biol Chem*, 280: 7581-7587.
122. Hung LY, Tang CJ, Tang TK (2000). Protein 4.1 R-135 interacts with a novel centrosomal protein (CPAP) which is associated with the gamma-tubulin complex. *Mol Cell Biol*, 20: 7813-7825.